

August 31, 2021

Solutions to Improve Business Performance of Vietnamese Textile and Garment Enterprises

Author Details: Duc Hoa Nguyen
Graduate Institute, National Economics University

Received Date: 12-Aug-2021 Accepted Date: 28-Aug-2021 Published Date: 31-Aug-2021

Abstract:

The objective of the study is to assess the current state of corporate culture and business performance of Vietnamese textile and garment enterprises. From there, the study provides solutions and recommendations to improve the business performance of Vietnamese textile and garment enterprises.

Keywords: *Corporate culture, performance, Vietnam textile*

1. Introduction

In order to stand firmly in the market, many textile and garment enterprises have applied creatively to build a strong organizational culture; constantly invest in building organizational culture to nurture and attract talents, prevent human loss and brain drain. Recently, the development of organizational culture has become a widely and methodically implemented action in many textile and garment enterprises in Vietnam. When enterprises expand their activities to the "multicultural" market, the organizational cultural advantages become the strength of the enterprise, strongly affecting the attitudes and working behaviors of employees. Therefore, textile and garment enterprises need to build a methodical organizational culture and contain long-term values, helping employees to be self-aware of being attached to the organization that will bring them valuable values. future and help customers be more satisfied and loyal to the business, thereby helping to improve business performance for the business.

In addition, many businesses follow pragmatism, regardless of tricks to achieve high profits in business, including violations of the law, or production that affects consumers' health. Over the years, in different fields, many companies have been discovered for economic profit despite directly discharging untreated wastewater into the environment, causing extremely negative impacts on people's lives and surroundings. Typically, Formosa Ha Tinh enterprise discharged hazardous wastes into the sea, leading to mass fish deaths and heavy environmental pollution in 2016.

In addition, many businesses have not attached importance to the role of the collective, the meaning of the lesson of national unity handed down from the past to the present, leading to the weak business situation of some Vietnamese textile and garment enterprises. From the wrong way of thinking, these businesses were quickly eliminated, especially in the context of fierce competition in terms of quality and price in the market today.

Therefore, improving the organizational culture in Vietnam's textile and garment enterprises is necessary and urgent in the face of the strong development of the times.

2. Reality about Vietnam's textile and garment enterprises

After peace was restored in 1954, the North of the country was completely liberated, creating favorable conditions for economic development to serve the process of liberating the South and reunifying the country.

At this stage, the Party and Government paid special attention to and invested in the development of Vietnam's textile and garment industry. A series of high-productivity textile and garment businesses have been improved and developed with the support of socialist countries such as: Weaving 8-3, Knitting Dong Xuan,

August 31, 2021

Weaving Vinh Phu, Garment 10, Weaving. Nam Dinh, Thang Long Garment... Besides, craft production groups and cooperatives have been conducted to meet the garment needs of the people.

The country's reunification in 1975 has created opportunities for improvement and development for Vietnam's textile and garment industry. A series of skilled personnel from the Central to the South have been added to the textile industry. New factories such as Hanoi Yarn, Hue Yarn, Vinh Yarn, Viet Tien Garment, Nha Trang Yarn, Huu Nghi Garment... have been built.

However, there are many limitations in the textile and garment industry in this period. In the context of economic implementation under the general mechanism, textile and garment enterprises produce according to the general criteria issued by the state, there has not been any flexible change and innovation in the process of enterprise management and commodity production. Attention and investment in product development and innovation to improve operational productivity have not yet been focused. Textile products during this period mainly met domestic demand and exported to Eastern Europe.

In the context that diplomacy has not been really expanded but only had relations with socialist countries before 1990, Vietnam's textile and garment industry mainly produced for domestic demand and exported to Eastern European countries. When the country moved from a centralized economy to a market economy, businesses across the country faced many challenges, especially state-owned enterprises.

With a subsidized bureaucracy, enterprises in this mechanism are provided with capital and inputs, production activities are based on given criteria and outputs. This production mechanism has caused difficulties for enterprises with major disadvantages such as: insufficient working capital, outdated production skills, underdeveloped technology and small production scale. Because of not being able to adapt to the new context, many businesses operate at a loss and have a high probability of bankruptcy.

In addition, the State's macro policies during this period were issued with remarkable highlights, typically the Law on Foreign Investment in Vietnam. With the policy to encourage foreign investment, the textile and garment industry has received a large amount of investment capital. Foreign direct investment (FDI) under the joint venture model is the main form of investment in the textile and garment industry. This is a big step forward for Vietnamese enterprises in general and enterprises in the textile and garment industry in Vietnam in particular because this policy has created favorable conditions for Vietnamese enterprises to access and apply modern technologies. and more efficient business management system. From this special event, the textile industry is changed in both quantity and quality. Along with the rapid growth, the export market has opened up many opportunities for Vietnam's textile and garment industry. The scope of export is no longer restricted to socialist countries in Eastern Europe, but also to potential markets such as Japan, EU, ASEAN... In addition, joining international organizations It is also one of the reasons for the remarkable progress of Vietnam's textile and garment industry: WTO (1994), ASEAN (1995), ASEM (1996)...

If Vietnam's textile and garment industry was formed and shaped in the period before 1998, after this time, Vietnam's textile and garment industry officially entered the development stage. Especially during this period, Vietnam accelerated its expansion and participation in major markets in the world. Vietnam continued to participate in admission to major international organizations such as APEC (November 1998) and the bilateral trade agreement between Vietnam and the United States, which took effect in 2001. According to the data of the General Administration of According to statistics in 2001, the total number of enterprises of the textile and garment industry was more than 1000 enterprises and increased to about 8000 enterprises in 2016. From 1998 to present, the average growth rate of the number of textile enterprises in Vietnam is 17%/year.

According to data from the International Trade Center (ITC), Vietnam ranks fourth in terms of total export value of textile products. The textile industry in Vietnam has an advantage in the world textile industry thanks to its abundant and cheap labor force. However, Vietnam is gradually losing this advantage because labor costs in Vietnam are increasing gradually over the years. In 2019, the basic salary increased by 5-8%, creating a significant financial burden for businesses.

Currently, Vietnam's textile and garment industry has participated in the process of comprehensive integration and an equal competitive environment with textile enterprises in the world. To have a competitive

August 31, 2021

advantage in the international market, the Vietnamese textile and garment industry needs to rely on sustainable growth and development strategies. One of the tools the industry has used over the years is the quantity and quality of human resources in Vietnam.

Vietnam's textile and garment industry has labor-intensive characteristics, especially the garment industry. As of 2017, 9,826 textile and garment enterprises have been built and operated with an actual workforce of more than 1.8 million people.

The characteristic of human resources has contributed great achievements to the growth in export value of the textile and garment industry in Vietnam. Especially in the period 2009 - 2013 when the world textile and garment market was affected by the financial crisis, but the growth rate of the textile and garment industry not only did not decrease but also doubled: USD 10,416 billion (2009.) to USD 21.215 billion (2013) (according to the General Department of Customs) and tripled in the period 2010 - 2017. The origin of this achievement is because labor productivity and product quality of the textile industry have been improved. improve during this period. Labor productivity (based on export value) from 12,755 USD/person/year (2010) to 17,042 USD/person/year (2017). In addition, the processing and selling prices during this period continuously decreased by about 5%-10% per year. The data in Figure 4.4 shows that the state budget has supported textile and garment training schools up to more than 485 billion VND. This figure is only about 23 million USD, but it has brought an impressive increase to the export value of the textile and garment industry: from 13,304 billion USD (2010) to 31.284 billion USD (2017), an increase of nearly 18 billion USD.

According to the 2015 Statistical Yearbook, the number of enterprises in Vietnam's textile and garment industry is 8,770, accounting for about 2% of the total number of enterprises in the country, of which there are only nearly 30 enterprises with a dynamic loudspeaker scale of more than 5,000 people. However, the number of employees in the industry is about 1.6 million people, accounting for nearly 5% of the total labor force of the country. However, the income of workers in the textile and garment industry in Vietnam has not been paid with a commensurate salary: 5.6 million VND/person/month in the textile sector, 5.0 million VND/person/month in the garment sector. This figure is lower than the average income of workers in the economic sector (6.3 million VND/person/month).

According to the Vietnam Textile and Apparel Association (Vitas), dozens of countries around the world have invested in the textile and garment industry in Vietnam. In which, the total amount of foreign direct investment in this industry is up to 1,546 billion USD with 184 different projects in the first 11 months of 2019. Among the countries with the leading amount of investment capital in the textile industry In Vietnam, the most prominent are five big countries: Hong Kong (\$0.45 billion), Singapore (\$0.3370 billion), China (\$0.270 billion), South Korea (\$0.165 billion) and Seychelles (\$0.103 billion). In addition, other developed countries have also registered investment capital in Vietnam's textile and garment industry, such as Japan, the United States, etc.

Areas attracting a large amount of FDI into Vietnam's textile and garment industry include: Tay Ninh has 16 projects (464 million USD), Quang Nam 10 projects (\$107 million USD), Nghe An has 3 projects (210 million USD). USD).

According to statistics of the General Department of Customs, the export value of textile and garment enterprises attracting FDI reached 17.6 billion USD, accounting for 58.9% of the total export value of the textile and garment industry across the country. The attraction of FDI not only brings advantages in the ability to access and apply modern technology to enterprises, but also helps businesses have stable output.

According to the Ministry of Industry and Trade, Vietnam's textile and garment industry has nearly 1,390 FDI projects with a registered capital of 6.12 billion USD in 2012. The period 2014-2015 is a time of great development of enterprises. attracting FDI. Only in 2014, with the trend of shifting investment to the textile and garment sector to pursue major Trade Agreements, attracted USD 1.64 billion for 83 FDI projects in the textile and garment industry, bringing a 20% increase to production capacity and continues to increase over the years.

3. Solution

3.1. Building an internal culture in the business

Internal corporate culture is the foundation for building and developing resources for enterprises, creating favorable conditions to improve the sense of responsibility and labor results of employees. So, to develop the internal culture in the business, the topic offers some solutions below.

Attitude is a key element in building corporate culture. In business, ethical standards of conduct should be upheld. For leaders, it is necessary to improve management capacity and orientation for employees. As a true leader, it is necessary to care and understand employees, ensure good and friendly behavior towards employees, be ethical and responsible even in the corporate environment and beyond social life. Managers and leaders are not only capable and highly specialized, but also build principles and consistency in action. At the same time, leaders also need to have the ability to motivate and encourage employees to work and contribute actively.

Employees are the main labor force that creates product value in textile enterprises in Vietnam. The enterprise itself has built a positive culture expressed through the spirit and responsibility of employees. Employees need to be proactive, actively working and creative, regularly accumulating and improving professional knowledge, towards a spirit of hard work and efficiency. Not only need to have a high sense of responsibility and expertise, for employees with each other or between employees and managers, leaders need to show respect, help each other to work and develop. Business leadership must ensure trust for employees, customers and partners. Trust is the basis of long-term cooperation, demonstrating the satisfaction of employees and customers for the business. It is easy to see that employees who have trust and satisfaction with the company will have a desire to stick with the business for a long time. Customers trust the business to build customer loyalty to the business, this is the core factor to maintain the love and support of customers.

In order to regularly improve the attitude and professionalism of employees, Vietnamese enterprises, especially in the textile and garment sector, need to periodically organize corporate culture courses for both employees and managers leader. These courses help employees understand their own role as well as the management's concern for employees in the business. In addition, businesses need to avoid situations where sanctions are not transparent and clear, causing internal disunity as well as employee trust.

Enterprises need to focus on building the collective spirit, upholding the tradition of national solidarity, especially the individuals in the enterprise. To build this spirit, businesses can join business associations - where to exchange and help solve difficult problems that businesses themselves cannot solve. overcome the outstanding weaknesses in the business. The collective spirit factor ensures that the enterprise becomes a unified, coherent and consistent individual, thereby developing good business performance.

Because the culture in the business originates from the smallest factors. Therefore, it is necessary to develop and apply a code of conduct in the company. The Code is built on the basis of ensuring the common interests of all parties, towards building a fair, friendly and healthy working environment, accompanying the development of enterprises. In addition, the uniform working spirit among employees spreads positive energy to everyone, resulting in high results at work.

3.2. Building a concept to adapt to the market culture, aiming at the goal of "customer-centered"

It must be affirmed that Vietnamese enterprises, including the textile and garment industry, in order to achieve high profits, need to well meet the needs of the market. The market is a place to exchange, buy and sell goods on the basis of the satisfaction of economic entities involved in activities. A business that produces goods that do not meet the needs of the market, the tastes of customers, cannot generate revenue or profit. The enterprises that grasp the trend of the market are the ones that hold a high market share in the trading market. Therefore, it is necessary to consider the needs of the market as the point of birth and the starting point of organizational

August 31, 2021

culture. Enterprises that want to create a competitive advantage need to grasp the development trend of the market well, thereby taking the basis of improving product innovation according to customer needs.

Moreover, customers are always considered a key factor that textile enterprises in particular and all businesses need to aim. Because customers are the people who consume the company's products. Taking customers as the center is the statement of development goals at businesses.

Based on that, Vietnamese textile and garment enterprises need to improve the quality of customer service through the variety of designs and quality of textile products, creating trust, satisfaction and customer loyalty to the company's brand.

In order to be able to grasp market development trends, businesses have the ability to analyze, research and evaluate market movements in the apparel sector, especially the complexity of the international market. Continuous innovation, creative thinking, proactively adapting to the rapid changes of the market. Improving research, analysis and evaluation capacity is not easy. Textile and garment enterprises need to invest in science and technology, apply technological advances to product research and development...

Currently, the market is constantly fluctuating under the influence of many factors, such as the global impact of Covid-19 or the moves of the US and China in the US-China trade war, etc. Therefore, businesses also need to train and improve the management and leadership capacity of managers, ensure the right and appropriate decisions and make smart strategies in the context of the times creating a new step in the production and business of textiles and garments of Vietnamese enterprises.

In addition, anticipating market trends will be made even better, when businesses invest in building specialized departments to conduct research, evaluate and provide scenarios to cope with changes. above. However, not all businesses focus on investing in predictive analysis and market research development. Because this is a fairly large investment and does not bring immediate profits to the business, but towards long-term development goals. Even so, this is a wise strategy towards raising the status of a business in the long term. Therefore, it is necessary and important to grasp the market culture and put the consumer at the center.

3.3. Solutions to develop a culture of innovation and creativity in the enterprise

In recent years, the world has brought many valuable articles to Vietnam's textile and garment enterprises with spectacular "switching of thrones" among famous global enterprises. Specifically, the sudden disappearance of the companies. Large technology corporations such as Nokia, Yahoo... Instead, the strong rise of powerful empires such as Google, Facebook, etc. The reason for this amazing transformation is the breakthrough in energy, innovation and creativity. Therefore, it is undeniable that the strategic role of changing the position of innovation capacity in enterprises cannot be denied.

Innovation is always a strategic goal that leaders aim to build into a culture in their organizations and businesses. Innovation creates a driving force for the development of unique products, attracting a high market share of consumers, thereby creating outstanding development on the basis of creativity and innovation. Next, thanks to innovation, creativity creates a highly competitive advantage for businesses, especially Vietnamese textile and garment enterprises with a rich diversity in products. Creating competitive advantage by other methods is considered difficult to implement. Innovation and creativity are indispensable requirements to decide the development or be eliminated from the fiercely competitive market today. Not focusing on the role of innovation is to bring businesses to the brink of being wiped out from the market.

Realizing the important role of innovation and creativity, however, building such a culture is not easy. Leaders face many difficulties in creating and developing a culture of innovation and creativity. The following are some measures to improve the innovation and creativity capacity of textile and garment enterprises in Vietnam.

First, leaders must have a spirit of change towards innovation. The leader is the oil ship, pioneering the system of employees to learn and follow. To create a breakthrough in products, dominate the consumer market, and at the same time face risks that have a significant impact on business activities of enterprises. The process

August 31, 2021

of conducting innovation requires training to unlock the hidden potential in the workforce. Innovation is a process, not a temporary one, therefore, it is necessary to create an overall environment to change the creative thinking of each individual. The creative spirit can be harnessed through individual or team creativity competitions.

Second, the innovation needs to be set goals, avoiding the case of unclear and ineffective innovation. The construction of specific, clear, and measurable goals is a prerequisite for ensuring the innovation process to achieve outstanding efficiency.

Third, innovation does not have to happen alone, between individuals. Collaboration and communication have the effect of promoting creative and innovative ideas. Through, communication, discussion makes ideas somewhat more complete, creativity becomes more creative. Moreover, an innovative enterprise is that all members are creative, the whole system is creative.

Fourth, leaders need to grasp the capacity of employees, thereby assigning the right work according to their wishes to maximize creativity in work.

Finally, another factor that stimulates creativity is the reward policy. This shows the appreciation of employees' efforts in the working environment, stimulates the spirit of competition between individuals and groups, thereby being a lever to promote the development of a common creative culture in the business. Karma.

3.4. Dynamic capacity development solutions

Dynamic capacity is one of the internal capabilities of each individual or enterprise. Dynamic capacity is reflected in the capacity of strategy formulation, creative research and management capacity. Dynamic competencies play an important role in enhancing organizational culture.

To improve the dynamic capacity of textile enterprises in Vietnam, the thesis proposes some solutions as follows:

- Firstly, encourage members to improve their spirit of accumulating experience and promptly adapting to market fluctuations.
- Second, accumulating dynamic capacity is a process, therefore, developing dynamic capacity in an enterprise is also a process that requires a lot of time. Leaders need to organize programs and activities to improve dynamic capacity in each individual.
- Thirdly, the attention of leaders is the motivation to encourage employees to try to promote dynamic capacity in organizations and enterprises.
- Fourth, promote innovative research in enterprises to create a premise for developing dynamic capacity in enterprises.
- Finally, leadership capacity of managers is a decisive factor for the development of dynamic capacity. Therefore, continue to improve and regularly practice the management capacity of leaders. Through the courses on management capacity is a specific example of the solution to improve dynamic capacity.

3.5. Solutions to improve business efficiency of Vietnamese textile and garment enterprises

The textile and garment industry, as stated above, plays an important role in contributing to the surplus value of export turnover, and is an important part of the country's economy. In order for the textile industry to overcome difficulties and develop sustainably, the study proposes the following solutions:

Firstly, applying science and technology is an indispensable condition to improve the business efficiency of textile and garment enterprises in Vietnam. The application of technology to the production process and product packaging needs to be focused and continuously innovated to meet market needs. Thanks to the application of technology leading to high profit margin by reducing production costs. In addition, businesses need to focus on cooperation, solidarity and development in a fair and healthy environment. The development of human resources also needs more attention because people are an important factor in the production process, improving product value.

August 31, 2021

Second, the Vietnam Textile and Apparel Association needs to do a good job of linking businesses, creating conditions for development in both domestic and international markets. The Association is a place to solve and remove difficulties in individual businesses, and at the same time, it is also a place to solicit opinions and recommendations of businesses to the Government's management agencies. Improving the operational efficiency of the association is to improve the economic performance of enterprises.

Third, state agencies need to reform administrative procedures, reduce and organize the legal ground closely but without cumbersome, complete and clear. The management and intervention of the government is necessary to ensure an effective and beneficial business environment for businesses. At the same time, in order to fully exploit the benefits from the free trade agreements signed by Vietnam, it is necessary to unify the legal system as well as develop appropriate policies in a timely manner to maximize capacity. of enterprises in the period of international cooperation. From the attention and intervention of the State, creating great confidence for businesses, they also believe in improving business efficiency, contributing to bringing Vietnam's economy firmly on the growth momentum.

The State needs to strictly regulate the legal framework to ensure the fair development of enterprises in accordance with the principles and orientations set by the Government. It is necessary to well control the problem of waste treatment and environmental pollution in order to achieve the goal of economic development but still ensure environmental conditions. As mentioned above, development must go hand in hand with environmental protection, the Government needs to closely review and have strict sanctions against organizations and businesses for economic benefits regardless of environmental impacts. shared.

The State can also organize contests or award certificates of merit to businesses that are active in innovation, especially innovation that has a positive impact on the environment. Thus, the state can both encourage businesses to innovate and stimulate action to protect the environment. Thanks to the reforms in government policies, it will create favorable conditions for the development of general efficiency in the economy.

Fourth, build, improve and enhance the role of supply chain value in the domestic textile and garment system. The development of the supply chain is the premise for the initiative in the supply of raw materials and the production process. From the capacity to proactively create conditions to promote the innovation and creativity of enterprises mentioned earlier, thereby improving the business performance of enterprises. Only then will Vietnam be able to maintain its position as an exporter of textiles and garments in the world market and continue to strive for excellence in the future.

Fifth, the whole textile industry towards stable and sustainable development, conquering the fastidious standards of the international market. Conquering the international market is always the goal in all fields, this is the way towards future development as well as affirming the quality of Vietnamese textile and garment products to other countries. Since then, promoting the brand as well as positively affecting the attraction of foreign investment capital more effectively and with better quality, making Vietnam an ideal land to attract investors to come and invest development.

4. Proposing recommendations to improve business efficiency of Vietnamese textile and garment enterprises

4.1. For the State

Firstly, the state strengthens amendments and establishes the coherence of the legal framework. Ensure businesses operate in a healthy, fair and efficient environment.

Secondly, timely supplement policies to support businesses in the face of the increasingly complex Covid-19 pandemic in order to concretize the policies of the Party and State to people and businesses.

Policies to support businesses need to be implemented properly and meaningfully, avoiding misplaced and ineffective support and putting the State under more pressure. The State promotes support in the direction of focusing on the right subjects and the level of damage of enterprises. The textile and garment industry is

August 31, 2021

currently heavily affected by the Covid-19 impact due to the disruption in the supply of production materials, before the State's distancing directive, and the way textile and garment enterprises have almost stalled all activities. Therefore, policies at this time are urgent, such as low-interest loans, tax reduction support, etc. in order to facilitate the recovery of economic activities in the near future.

For the policies that have been implemented, it is necessary to review and grasp the effectiveness, assigning responsibility for checking and answering questions to ministries and branches, ensuring the timeliness and effectiveness, and avoiding negative impacts of the policies. time lag affects the effectiveness of policies. Adjust the limitations encountered in support work to optimize efficiency for businesses.

Thirdly, pay special attention to the activities of small and micro enterprises and provide support policies for this group such as loan support, support to improve the quality of employees professional action.

The US-China trade war and the Covid-19 pandemic have led to a shift in the supply chains of countries. Specifically, some countries such as the US, Japan, and South Korea are aiming to move part of the supply chain out of China. This creates favorable conditions for Vietnam when it has many advantages in terms of macroeconomic stability, geographical location, tight legal system... potential growth opportunities. Therefore, this is the time to develop and implement appropriate support policies for each target group.

Fourth, strengthen the preservation of ethnic cultural traditions. Specifically, the spirit of solidarity, determination, hard work, industriousness, enthusiasm in work ... From there, it contributes to influencing the employee's awareness system and corporate culture, arousing good virtues in employees. Vietnamese people from past to present, and apply effectively to labor work, dedication to enterprises and the state. These long-standing cultural traits have a positive impact on business performance, especially in the textile and garment sector.

Fifth, organize the organization of creative competitions of national stature, promoting creativity, innovation in labor and dedication to the country.

Finally, quickly deploy and complete the vaccination against COVID-19 for workers in textile and garment enterprises, to ensure disease prevention and continue production activities in accordance with regulations dual goals set by the Government.

4.2. For ministries, branches and localities

Firstly, the ministries and branches have well performed the supervision of the activities of enterprises in their respective areas.

The correct implementation is to ensure the operation of enterprises in accordance with the framework of the state. Conduct inspection and supervision of the operation, waste treatment criteria of textile enterprises. From there, it is possible to timely detect businesses that violate the law, or hide illegal acts to promptly handle. Avoid the phenomenon of detection too late, causing many negative impacts on the environment and people's lives around. Consequences on the environment are unpredictable, so early detection reduces the harmful effects of wrongdoing on the environment. In the face of increasingly serious environmental problems, the lack of awareness and responsibility of businesses to maximize profits at all costs is something that needs to be detected in time and severely punished. Avoid repetition of previous cases.

Secondly, strengthen cooperation and exchange ideas with textile and garment associations to grasp the situation, record opinions in a timely manner, and support the work of advising the Prime Minister to make wise decisions.

Textile and garment associations are the place to synthesize opinions and problems of textile and garment enterprises. Strengthening connections and receiving opinions helps ministries and branches have a realistic and close look at the activities of businesses. At the same time, support to answer questions promptly for businesses. Since then, ministries and branches have discovered loopholes in the management and administration of the state, thereby proposing amendments to the Prime Minister.

August 31, 2021

Third, actively synthesize, report and propose solutions to improve the efficiency of business operations. Ensure that the State makes timely adjustments to the context of the times.

4.3. For corporates

Firstly, businesses strengthen market research and develop marketing departments.

Market research is considered as the key for textile and garment business organizations to forecast the future market situation. Based on the forecast, businesses build scenarios to adapt to the change and set out business strategies in the future. In order to perform well the task of market research, enterprises need to ensure a force of qualified researchers with high professional capacity. Invest in building a separate research room, focusing on research, not in charge of synthesizing many other jobs in the research room, in order to improve the operational efficiency of the research room.

Recognizing the strategic role of market research, the problem of developing research tasks should be implemented in a timely manner, avoiding delay and indifference. To predict accurately, research must be consistent from management to employees, research on the basis of the system of the whole enterprise and the market. The research department meets the following criteria:

- The data collected in the research must be complete, accurate, and reflect the reality of the market
- System of competent, responsible, proactive and creative staff in research work
- Assess the market objectively, taking into account other factors affecting the change in the strategic scenario.

The marketing department decides on the product development strategy, is a key part in performing the task of innovation and creativity. Marketing department works effectively when there is close coordination between departments. The marketing department is responsible for communication, advertising, strategic customer access to test the market's reaction, launching promotional packages to stimulate demand for goods...

Second, set out product policies

In the face of the rapid development of science and technology, textile goods are increasingly diverse and rich in size, design, and color... Therefore, to make full use of the potential in market segments Enterprises need to do well in formulating effective product policies. An effective policy should be based on market research before the actual situation. From there, setting out appropriate policies, ensuring export standards in terms of product quality, quantity and price. Thereby, affirming the brand in the international market, improving the efficiency of the company's business activities. textile enterprises. Some notable product design policies include:

- The product design is suitable to the tastes of consumers, ensuring to impress and attract customers based on the research results of the research department.
- Meet the decentralization needs of the market
- Quality assurance products combined with promotional packages increase profit efficiency.
- Focus on developing a number of key products and brands of the business. Towards diversifying products but ensuring parallel development of strategic products, thereby reaching a wide range of customers while keeping the unique strengths of the business.

Third, develop a pricing policy suitable for the market segment, based on input costs, tax regulations of the State and the supply and demand level in the market. Price is a factor that determines the competitiveness of products, thereby affecting the quantity of products consumed.

Fourth, continuously improve the quality of labor resources

People are always a factor that is highly valued in the production process. Without the human factor, the business process is not guaranteed to operate effectively. Humans are the basis for operating modern machines and equipment. Currently, the country's orientation is towards workers mastering technology.

Fifth, strengthen economic linkages for cooperation and development.

August 31, 2021

The above are some recommendations for businesses towards sustainable and stable development, which is the foundation for promoting the development of the textile industry in general and of textile enterprises in particular.

5. Conclusion

Currently, there are many definitions of corporate culture. However, there is a most common understanding: Corporate culture is the entire cultural value built up during the existence and development of an enterprise, thereby becoming familiar rules and practices, deeply ingrained in the activities of the enterprise and at the same time governs the feelings, ways of thinking and behavior of all members in the enterprise in order to pursue and realize the common purpose.

Textile and garment are not only prominent in the field of export, but many brands have gradually become popular and made a good impression on domestic consumers such as Garment 10, Viet Tien, Nha Be, Phong Phu, Dong Xuan, Hanosimex... is the result of a process of efforts, confirmed through the quality, reputation of the product and also the intangible cultural values of each enterprise.

Like many other industries, the textile and garment enterprises build their culture from the most basic things such as: strictly complying with the provisions of the law, standards on OSH; carry out social responsibility; environmental protection... to things like balancing the interests between businesses, employees and consumers; fair competition in the market; repel negativity in production and business activities; encourage the spirit of entrepreneurship, creative labor...

Corporate culture has long been created and maintained by businesses and employees in the system, which is a solid foundation for the industry to develop sustainably with the biggest goal for employees, for the stability and prosperity of the business. . That culture becomes even more humane and meaningful when the Covid-19 epidemic breaks out in 2020. It is an industry that is directly and heavily affected, but with the spirit of "Volunteering to share with businesses, volunteering to reduce wages, reduce working hours, change, share job positions, even volunteer to work. no salary.", the textile industry still overcomes difficulties to "retain" employees, preserve the team, and maintain its position in the global supply chain.

References

- i. *The Ministry of Industry and Trade proposed Vitas to create an ecosystem for businesses (2020)*. Available at: <https://tapchicongthuong.vn/bai-viet/bo-cong-thuong-de-nghi-vitas-tao-ra-he-sinh-thai-cho-cac-doanh-nghiep-det-may-viet-nam-77292.htm> (Accessed: 14 September 2021).
- ii. *Bui Thi Thuy Duong, 2019, Update 2018 business results of textile industry*
- iii. *Colin C. J. Cheng, Chen-lung Yang, Chwen Sheu, 2014, The link between eco-innovation and business performance: a Taiwanese industry context*
- iv. *CristianeFroehlich, ClaudiaCristinaBitencourt, MariliaBonzaniniBossle, 2017, The use of dynamic capabilities to boost innovation in a Brazilian Chemical Company*
- v. *Do Thi Hien, 2017, Influence of corporate culture on financial performance of Phu Hoa An textile company*
- vi. *Solutions to improve production and business efficiency of Textile and Garment Company 7 - National Defense Journal (2021)*. Available at: <http://tapchiqptd.vn/en/tong-ket-thuc-tien-va-king-nghiem/giai-phap-nang-cao-hieu-qua-san-xuat-king-doanh-cua-cong-ty-det-may-7/9715.html> (Accessed: 14 September 2021).
- vii. *Proposal for early promulgation of the Strategy for Textile Industry Development 2030 - 2045 (2021)*. Available at: <https://baodautu.vn/kien-nghi-som-ban-hanh-chien-luoc-phan-trien-cong-nghiep-det-may-2030---2045-d143217.html> (Accessed: 14 September 2021).
- viii. *Kimberly Kuster Dale, 2012, PERCEPTIONS OF ORGANIZATIONAL CULTURE OF A MULTI-CAMPUS COMMUNITY COLLEGE DISTRICT: MIXED METHODS IN CONCERT*
- ix. *Le Hong Thuan, 2017, Textile industry report*

August 31, 2021

- x. Liao, Z., 2018. *Corporate culture, environmental innovation and financial performance. Business Strategy and the Environment*, 27(8), pp.1368-1375.
- xi. Marc Thompson and Paul Heron, 2005, *Management capability and high performance work organization*
- xii. *Some measures to improve business efficiency of enterprises (2021)*. Available at: <https://sapuwa.com/mot-so-bien-phap-nang-cao-hieu-qua-business-business-cua-cac-doanh-nghiep.html> (Accessed: 14 September 2021).
- xiii. Nguyen Hai Minh, 2015, *Corporate culture model at state-owned commercial banks before and after Vietnam joins WTO*
- xiv. Nguyen Tran Sy, 2013, *Dynamic capacity – a new approach to create competitive advantage for small and medium enterprises in Vietnam*
- xv. Nguyen Truong Son, Ngo Tan Nhi, Hoang Van Hai, 2021, *USING OCAI TOOLS TO ASSESS CORPORATE CULTURE - CASE STUDY AT DATRACO COMPANY*
- xvi. Richard Yu Yuan Hung et al, 2010, *Dynamic capability: Impact of process alignment and organizational learning culture on performance*
- xvii. Ruth Maria Stock & Bjoern Six & Nicolas A. Zacharias, 2013, *Linking multiple layers of innovation-oriented corporate culture, product program innovativeness, and business performance: a contingency approach*
- xviii. Stella wairimu muhura, 2012, *a research project submitted in partial fulfilment of the requirements for the award of the degree of master of business administration (mba), school of business, university of nairobi*